

Pword-report

Language name: **Pacoh** [pa'kɔh] (LID 2268)
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 Sources: Internet version of The Ethnologue, Vol. 15 (2005). www.ethnologue.com.
 Alves, Mark John (2000) *A Pacoh Analytic Grammar*. PhD dissertation, University of Hawai'i.
 Date completed: 30.05.2006

I Language profile

of spks: 16'000 in Vietnam (2002), 13'224 in Laos (1995)
 place: Quang Tri Province/VN; Saravan, Savannakhet Provinces/LAO
 Contact lgs.: Vietnamese
 Status: no official language
 Prospects: in Laos 70% are monolingual, in VN most people are bilingual in Vietnamese
 Struct. results: many loans from Vietnamese, in Vietnam the language is dying out

II Morpheme types

1. _____ Stem
2. _____ Restricted pre-posed formative

Pronouns take a prefix ʔa- (~ (ω ʔadɔː)- for DAT, and ʔN- (~ (ω ʔndɔː)- for POSS. The long form occurs with disyllabic pronominal stems, the short form with monosyllabic ones. A pronoun with the short prefix yield a single pword, those with the long prefix yield two pwords (due to minimal and maximal word requirements).

Table 1. Pronoun system of Pacoh.

Person/ Number	General Pronoun	DAT	POSS
Singular			
1s	<i>ki:</i>	<i>ʔa-ki:</i>	<i>ʔŋ-ki:</i>
2s	<i>maj</i>	<i>ʔa-maj</i>	<i>ʔm-maj</i>
3s	<i>dɔ:</i>	<i>ʔa-dɔ:</i>	<i>ʔn-dɔ:</i>
Dual			
1d	<i>naŋ</i>	<i>ʔa-naŋ</i>	<i>ʔŋ-naŋ</i>
2d	<i>ʔina:</i>	<i>ʔadɔː-ʔina:</i>	<i>ʔndɔː-ʔina:</i>
3d	<i>ʔana:</i>	<i>ʔadɔː-ʔana:</i>	<i>ʔndɔː-ʔana:</i>
Plural			
1p	<i>hɛ:</i>	<i>ʔa-hɛ:</i>	<i>ʔŋ-hɛ:</i>
2p	<i>ʔipe:</i>	<i>ʔadɔː-ʔipe:</i>	<i>ʔndɔː-ʔipe:</i>
3p	<i>ʔape:</i>	<i>ʔadɔː-ʔape:</i>	<i>ʔndɔː-ʔape:</i>
or	<i>ŋa:j</i>	<i>ʔa-ŋa:j</i>	<i>ʔŋ-ŋa:j</i>

→ 2 morpheme types

III Syllable

Syllable structure

The stress syllable template is (C₁)C₂V₁(V₂)(C₃) with the following restrictions:

- C₁ can be /p, t, k/ and can only be filled when C₂ = /l, r/, the cluster /tl/ is disallowed, *plɔh* 'to ask', *prɛ:ŋ* 'dry', *tru:* 'deep', *klitŋ* 'many', *krum* 'thunder'.
- C₂ obligatorily filled, can be every consonant phoneme except /w^ʔ/ and /j^ʔ/
- V₁ obligatorily filled, can be every vowel phoneme
- V₂ can be /ə/ only (but phonetically it becomes [a, ɛ, ə] in certain contexts), or it can be filled by vowel length

- C₃ can be /p, t, c, k, ʔ, ɛ, h, m, n, ŋ, l, r, w, j, wʔ, jʔ/ (all stop phonemes are neutralized to voiceless unaspirated, unreleased stops)

The so called presyllable, which is always unstressed, has the template C₁V₁(C₂) with many restrictions:

- C₁ can be /p, t, c, k, ʔ, m, ŋ, ŋ, l, r/, in reduplicated forms also {b, ɟ, ɛ, w}, {d, n} are not attested but seem to be not phonotactically excluded. Aspirated stops, /h/, /j/, /wʔ/ and /jʔ/ can not occur in this position.
- V₁ can be /i, u, a/ if C₂ is empty
/ə/ if C₂ is filled,
and /m, ŋ, ɲ, ɲ, l, r/ if C₁ is /ʔ/ and C₂ is empty.
The syllabic nasals are homorganic to the initial consonant of the main syllable (ŋ before /h ʔ/). [l] and [r] mostly occur before /l, r/, respectively.
- C₂ can be a nasal being homorganic to the initial consonant of the main syllable (ŋ before /h ʔ/) or /l, r/ mostly before /l, r/, respectively. C₂ can only be filled, if V₁ is a full vowel.

Every syllable has an onset, every stressed syllable has two morae!

Word requirements

- Since every stressed syllable has two morae, a minimal word also must have two morae.
- A pword can have only one single main syllable with an optional presyllable. Thus the maximum word is disyllabic.

Vowel-initial words

Do not occur since all syllables must have an onset.

Polysyllabic morphemes

cf. prefix *ʔa.də:-* 'DAT' (cf. table 1 above), stems like *ʔa.dʒæ* [ʔa'dʒaj^h] 'monkey'

Phonotactics

cf. "Syllable structure" above. Initial /ŋ/ even occurs in function words: *ŋaj* 'they'

Superheavy syllables

Superheavy syllables can only occur in stressed (main) syllables, thus word-finally: *pre:ŋ* 'dry', *puəh* 'white'

IV Tone & Stress

Tone

No tonal distinctions are found.

Stress

Every main syllable bears primary stress and is word-final. No secondary stress is assigned.

V Other Non-concatenative Processes

Ablaut

The demonstratives exhibit length ablaut between medial and distal forms:

Table 2. Medial and distal demonstratives.

	fore/higher	aft/lower	beside
MEDIAL	<i>ʔn.tih</i>	<i>ʔn.təh</i>	<i>ʔn.trah</i>
DISTAL	<i>ʔn.ti:h</i>	<i>ʔn.tə:h</i>	<i>ʔn.trɑ:h</i>

List of all phonological processes

1. _____ Coda stop neutralization (domain = φ or ω?)

[-son, -cont] → [-vcd, -asp, -released] / ______o

(1) /ce:t/ → [ce:t̚] 'pen'

The rule applies at the right edge of every syllable, but since presyllables cannot have a stop coda, it can only apply to the main syllables and thus word- and foot-finally.

2. _____ Palatalization (domain = φ or ω)

$/\epsilon/ \rightarrow [j^h \sim j] / ____ \sigma$

(2) $/\text{?u:\epsilon}/ \rightarrow [\text{?u:j}^h] \sim [\text{?u:j}]$ 'firewood'

With this rule, the same domain problem as with the first one can be observed.

3. _____ Labialization (domain = φ or ω)

$/k \eta/ \rightarrow [k^w \eta^w] / u, o ____ \#$

(3) $/du\eta/ \rightarrow [du\eta^w]$ 'house'

Every right edge of a foot is the right edge of a pword. Thus the domain remains unclear.

4. _____ Spirantization (domain = φ or ω ?)

$/w/ \rightarrow [v] / \# ____$

(4) $/wi:/ \rightarrow [vi:]$ 'to have'

No example for change in the presyllable is given, but this rule might be the best candidate for domain= ω .

VI "Free" Grammatical Morphemes

All particles like for instance numeral classifiers (which are nouns like *tikuaj* 'person') behave like proper pwords.

VII Polymorphemic Stem forms

With pronouns, the forms containing monosyllabic prefix+monosyllabic stem form a single pword with the unstressed presyllable *?a*. The forms with the disyllabic prefix *?adɔ:-* consist of two pwords.

VIII Compounds, Concatenations, Juxtapositions

No change in wordhood by dint of juxtaposition or compounding.

IX Reduplication

There are four different types of reduplication.

1. _____ Template Reduplication
(only with monosyllabic roots)

Full reduplication of the syllable template, sometimes with alternation of onset, vowel or coda. The resulting gword always consists of two separate pwords.

- (5) repetitive: $\epsilon\partial: \sim \epsilon\partial:$ 'pleasant'
- (6) rhyming: $t\partial k \sim v\partial k$ 'endless amount'
- (7) ablauted: $pu:c \sim pa:c$ 'flutter'
- (8) alliterative: $k^h\eta \sim k^h\epsilon r$ 'push rice into mouth continuously'
- (9) onset-vowel: $kr\partial:\eta \sim kr\partial:w$ 'property'

Alternation patterns are not identifiable.

2. Presyllabic Reduplication
(only with monosyllabic roots)

Copy of the first stem consonant + a. The resulting gword is one single pword.

- (10) *pa~pi:t* 'big (of a group of things)'
ka~ket 'small (of a group of things)'

3. Partial Reduplication
(rarely attested)

Copy of the main syllable, the presyllable remains. The resulting gword has two separate pwords.

- (11) *kənti?~ti?* 'sometimes'
tərkɪt~kɪt 'be close to'

4. Template+Presyllabic Reduplication
(rarely attested, only with monosyllabic roots)

Full copy of the monosyllabic root and interposing of *-ʔi-*. The resulting gword consists of two separate pwords, the second one contains the presyllable *ʔi*.

- (12) *vjəl~ʔi~vjəl* 'full of twists and bends'
ʔək~ʔi~ʔək 'raucous laughter'
ca:~ʔi~ca: 'to eat in general'

X **Phrase/Sentence-level phenomena**

The intonation peak within clauses is always on the verb.

- (13) *tóʔ* *ʔn.noh* *ki:* *dé:ʔ* *ʔn.noh*
arrive there so fall there
'When it reaches here, it falls down here.'

Non-interrogative statements have a falling pitch at the end, interrogative statements have a rising pitch at the end.

XI **Other Special things**

Geminates: only across syllable boundaries and only sonorants
Foot: trochaic feet (because in diphthongs the first part is the stressed one), every main syllable is one single foot, the presyllable is unfooted!

Evidence for: μ (min. constraint), σ (several rules), $\varphi \sim \omega$ (several rules, stress).